

EVALUATION OF TECHNICAL AND VOCATIONAL EDUCATION AND TRAINING (TVET) IN CORRECTIONAL CENTRES IN NORTH-WEST NIGERIA.

¹ Maryam Mannir Sani, ² P. S. Yaduma, ³A. M. Mshelia, ⁴J. M. Chedi

Department of Construction Technology Education,
Faculty of Technology Education, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi,
Bauchi State

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluates the implementation and impact of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) in correctional centres across North-West Nigeria. *The study was guided by two specific objectives with their corresponding research questions and null hypotheses. In carrying out this investigation, evaluative survey research design was used. The population of the study was eleven thousand, six hundred and seventy-six (11,676) respondents comprised 83 Instructors, 9,600 Inmates and 1,993 Ex-convicts of the North-Western Correctional Centres. Based on the population, the sample size was three hundred and seventy-five (375) respondents, which comprised 83 instructors (the whole instructors were used because the number is manageable), 140 Inmates and 152 Ex-convicts were selected from the seven (7) correctional centres of the seven North-Western states using purposive sampling technique. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer the research question and analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The result revealed that: technical and vocational education training programmes modules are efficient, the instructors of the programmes are adequate and the facilities in correctional centres in North-West, Nigeria are less adequate. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that: if adequate facilities were not provide in the correctional Centre in North-West, Nigeria, the objectives of programme will not be accomplishes Therefore, the study recommended among others, that the Government and all relevant stakeholders should provide adequate facilities and encourage all instructors of Technical and Vocational Education Training programmes in Correctional Centre in North-West, Nigeria to ensure contents coverage as the training modules of the programme as scheduled.*

INTRODUCTION

The growing prison population in Nigeria necessitates sustainable rehabilitation strategies that ensure inmates are reformed and reintegrated into society. Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) has been globally acknowledged as an effective tool for empowerment and rehabilitation (UNESCO, 2020). In Nigeria, the Nigerian Correctional Service Act (2019) recognizes vocational training as a key reform mechanism. However, the extent and effectiveness of TVET programs in correctional centres, especially in the North-West geopolitical zone, remain under-researched.

The North-West region, comprising states like Kano, Kaduna, Katsina, Zamfara, Sokoto, Jigawa, and Kebbi, is marked by high incarceration rates and limited employment opportunities—further emphasizing the need for effective rehabilitative education Akinwale, A. A. (2019). This paper, therefore, examines the valuation of TVET programs in correctional centres within this region, focusing on availability, effectiveness, and implementation challenges.

The Nigerian correctional system derives its existence from several statutes among which are the ordinance of 1916; laws of Nigeria, 1948 and 1958 and the existing correctional centre decree no. 9 of 1972. According to Opara (1998) the Nigerian correctional service is the promulgation of the correctional service decree no.9 of 1972. This was done in order to make the correctional service serve its triple purpose of confinement, reformation and rehabilitation. The decree according to the Annual correctional service report (1994) therefore specified the following objectives that should be performed in Nigerian correctional service.

- To keep safe custody of the inmates legally interned.
- To identify the causes of the anti-social behaviours, treat and reform inmates to become disciplined and law-abiding citizens of a free society.
- To train the inmates towards their rehabilitation on discharge and
- To generate funds to the government through correctional centre's farm and industry.

These objectives gave birth to the introduction of some directorates to carry out specialised functions needed to achieve the objectives of the correctional service. One such directorate is the directorate of inmates training and productivity. This is made agricultural and industry and charged with the responsibilities:

Studies show that successful TVET interventions in prisons can increase inmates' employability, reduce their likelihood of reoffending, and promote self-reliance post-release (Ezeajughu, 2021). However, without adequate tools, competent trainers, and appropriate curriculum, the potential of TVET in rehabilitation may be undermined Davis, L. M., Bozick, R., Steele, J. L., Saunders, J., & Miles, J. N. V. (2013). In the context of North-West Nigeria, characterized by high youth unemployment, security challenges, and weak correctional institutions, evaluating the effectiveness and sufficiency of TVET resources is imperative for both prison reform and societal development. To fill this literature gap, this study attempts to evaluate the technical and vocational education training programmes in correctional centres with specific reference to North-Western States of Nigeria. Recent studies that assessed the effectiveness of Technical and Vocational training in Correctional Centers in Nigeria using content, inputs process and products (CIPP) model for the study, it is considered a decision-making model that systematically collects information about strength

and limitations in content or delivery to improve programme effectiveness or plan for future of the programme...

Statement of the Problem

The inmates are expected to leave the Correctional Centres well reformed and rehabilitated and with vocational skills that will enable them to adopt to the society and live a life of self-sustaining, self-sufficiency and self-reliance and also become productive members of the society Davis, L. M., Bozick, R., Steele, J. L., Saunders, J., & Miles, J. N. V. (2013).

Prior research investigations observed that technical and vocational training programs have significance influence on the successful rehabilitation and reformation and re-integration of ex-inmates into their respective immediate societies Davis, L. M., Bozick, R., Steele, J. L., Saunders, J., & Miles, J. N. V. (2013). Correctional service facilities across North-Western States of Nigeria are experiencing enormous administrative problems that hinder inmates' welfare packages, overcrowding of inmates beyond the capacity of the facilities, inadequate health care services, unhealthy kitchen environment and most importantly, the absence of Technical and Vocational Training equipment. This assertion was confirmed by the National Human Rights Commission in its 2018 Prison report documents, where it was narrated that Funtua Prisons, Katsina State did not have any form of Technical and Vocational Facilities in place. The other Correctional Centres visited in the North-West have a limited number of Technical and Vocational Facilities with a combination of the following Vocational facilities: carpentry unit, tailoring unit, iron work unit, saloon/barbing, laundry, shoe making and knitting.

Based on prior existing related literature reviewed in this study, it was observed that Technical and Vocational Training Programme encountered problems which served as impediments towards the proper achievement of the programs. Ezeajughu, M. N. (2021). Olajide (2023) identified that the problems affecting Technical and Vocational Training Programs in Nigeria include; inadequate funding, inadequate facilities, lack of teaching materials and learning aids, lack of private investors, negative perception of the society, slow pace of technological growth, and lack of adequate professionally trained educators to ensure proper curriculum development. However, there was no research carried out on the evaluation of technical and vocational education training program in correctional centres with special reference to north-western states in Nigeria.

Purpose of the study

The aim of the study is to evaluate the technical and vocational training programmes in Correctional Centres in North-west, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Determine the adequacy of facilities for Technical and Vocational Education Training programmes in Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria.
2. Determine the efficacy of instructional methods used in training the Technical and Vocational Education Training Programmes in Correctional Centres in North-west, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. To what extent are adequacy Technical and Vocational Education Training programmes facilities in Correctional Centres in North- West Nigeria?

2. To what extent are the instructional methods of training (process) efficient in Technical and Vocational Education Training programmes in Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested by the study.

HO1: There is no significant difference between the mean response of the instructors, inmates and ex-convicts in regard to the adequacy of training facilities for Technical and Vocational Training programmes in Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria.

HO2: There is no significant difference between the mean response of the instructors, inmates and ex-convicts in regard to the efficient instructional methods of teaching used for Technical and Vocational Training programmes in Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria.

Methodology

A descriptive research design was used in the study. The study looked into the opinions and views of Instructors, Inmates and Ex-convicts of the North-Western Correctional Centres. To answer the research question, a structured questionnaire comprising 25 items was used for data collection. The questionnaire was validated by experts in the area. The reliability of the instrument was tested and it yielded a reliability index of 0.976. The population of the study was eleven thousand, six hundred and seventy-six (11,676) respondents comprised 83 Instructors, 9,600 Inmates and 1,993 Ex-convicts of the North-Western Correctional Centres. Based on the population, the sample size was three hundred and seventy-five (375) respondents, which comprised 83 instructors (the whole instructors were used because the number is manageable), 140 Inmates and 152 Ex-convicts were selected from the seven (7) correctional centres of the seven North-Western states using purposive sampling technique. 340 copies of the questionnaire were returned for data analysis. Therefore, the retrieval/response rate stands as 98% while the mortality rate stands as 2%. Hence, the analysis was computed based on 352 duly responded and retrieved. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze the demographic data of the respondents and answer the research questions and simple linear regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses stated in chapter one at 0.05 level of significance. Simple linear regression was used because the study is seeking impact of one independent variable on one dependent variable.

Results

Results of Research Questions

The results of research questions were presented in Tables 1 to 4

Research Question 1

To what extent are the Technical and Vocational Education Training programmes facilities in Correctional Centres adequate in North-west, Nigeria? This research question was answered using mean and standard deviation. **1.5** was used as a decision mean

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Respondents on to what Extent are the Technical and Vocational Education Training Programmes Facilities in Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria

S/N	Item Statement	X ₁	SD ₁	X ₂	SD ₂	X ₃	SD ₃	X _g	Remark
1.	The workshops are well-equipped with necessary tools and equipment.	2.81	.906	2.49	.705	2.41	.735	2.52	Adequate
2.	The classrooms are conducive to learning.	2.76	.892	2.45	.771	2.45	.719	2.51	Adequate
3.	The instructors are adequately trained to teach vocational skills.	2.14	.666	2.39	.717	2.45	.647	2.36	Less Adequate
4.	The learning materials are relevant and up to date.	2.30	.667	2.63	.713	2.34	.662	2.45	Less Adequate
5.	The electricity supply is reliable and sufficient.	2.14	.687	2.49	.754	2.44	.657	2.40	Less Adequate
Iron work									
6.	The ironwork equipment is in good working condition.	2.36	.703	2.46	.723	2.33	.669	2.39	Less Adequate
7.	The working tools are available and accessible to trainees.	2.44	.605	2.59	.720	2.41	.664	2.49	Less Adequate
8.	The working space is safe and well-ventilated.	2.44	.555	2.54	.714	2.36	.686	2.45	Less Adequate
9.	There are adequate instructors to supervise and guide trainees	2.61	.786	2.56	.850	2.42	.775	2.51	Adequate
Carpentry and Furniture making									
10.	The Tenon saw is available and in good working condition.	2.64	.660	2.56	.722	2.42	.736	2.52	Adequate
11.	The mortice saw is available and in good working condition.	2.74	.736	2.61	.793	2.42	.736	2.56	Adequate

12.	The hammer is available and in good working condition.	2.60	.710	2.61	.727	2.57	.717	2.59	Adequate
13.	The drilling machine is available and in good working condition.	2.57	.791	2.80	.797	2.54	.822	2.65	Adequate
14.	The workshop equipment is well-maintained	2.44	.735	2.37	.713	2.36	.706	2.38	Less Adequate
Car Wash									
15.	The car wash has a reliable water supply.	2.34	.720	2.43	.625	2.41	.631	2.40	Less Adequate
16.	The washing materials are available and of good quality.	2.47	.696	2.26	.723	2.30	.734	2.32	Less Adequate
17.	There is sufficient space for trainees to practice	2.59	.691	2.29	.713	2.29	.718	2.35	Less Adequate
18.	The laundry equipment is in good working condition	2.61	.666	2.26	.743	2.41	.744	2.39	Less Adequate
Barbing Saloon									
19.	The barbing salon has sufficient space for trainees to practice.	2.54	.755	2.24	.764	2.34	.848	2.34	Less Adequate
20.	The barbing materials are available and of good quality.	2.41	.670	2.26	.753	2.34	.752	2.32	Less Adequate
21.	The barbing tools are available and in good working condition.	2.60	.646	2.29	.735	2.34	.759	2.37	Less Adequate
22.	The safety materials are available and easily accessible.	2.61	.767	2.31	.759	2.45	.786	2.43	Less Adequate
Tailoring									
23.	The tailoring equipment is well-maintained.	2.51	.697	2.36	.702	2.48	.777	2.44	Less Adequate
24.	There is sufficient space for	2.4	.71	2.44	.712	2.38	.701	2.42	Less Adequate

	equipment and trainees.	7	7						e
25.	The sewing materials are available and of good quality.	2.40	.750	2.31	.759	2.47	.739	2.39	Less Adequate
Cap Making									
26.	The cap making materials are available and of good quality.	2.54	.716	2.31	.729	2.29	.749	2.35	Less Adequate
27.	The cap making tools are available and in good working condition.	2.70	.574	2.39	.802	2.31	.764	2.39	Less Adequate
Cap Washing									
28.	The cap washing has a reliable water supply	2.39	.767	2.36	.700	2.43	.707	2.39	Less Adequate
29.	The cap washing materials are available and of good quality	2.63	.705	2.34	.784	2.57	.792	2.49	Less Adequate
30.	The cap washing tools are in good working condition	2.64	.703	2.42	.857	2.43	.826	2.48	Less Adequate
Farming									
31.	The farming land is sufficient for practical training.	2.47	.653	2.32	.875	2.35	.798	2.36	Less Adequate
32.	The farm implements are available and in good working condition.	2.49	.697	2.44	.751	2.44	.698	2.46	Less Adequate
33.	The seeds are available and of good quality.	2.31	.649	2.50	.861	2.36	.826	2.41	Less Adequate
34.	The fertilizer is available and of good quality.	2.41	.602	2.41	.720	2.33	.690	2.39	Less Adequate
Poultry									
35.	The poultry area is well-ventilated and safe.	2.50	.794	2.51	.754	2.35	.753	2.44	Less Adequate

36.	The required tools for poultry are available and in good working condition.	2.50	.794	2.45	.790	2.35	.781	2.42	Less Adequate
37.	The water supply for poultry is reliable and sufficient.	2.57	.753	2.42	.778	2.29	.768	2.40	Less Adequate
Cluster Mean		2.51	.691	2.43	.752	2.40	.737	2.43	Less Adequate

Source: Field Work, 2025

Table 1 shows the Mean and Standard Deviation of the respondents on to what extent are the facilities of Technical and Vocational Training programmes in Correctional Centre in North-West, Nigeria. The table showed the mean of Instructors ranging from 2.14 to 2.81, the standard deviation also ranges from .555 to .906, the mean of Inmates also ranges from 2.24 to 2.80, the standard deviation ranges from .625 to .875 and the mean of Ex-convicts ranges from 2.29 to 2.57, the standard deviation also ranges from .631 to .848 respectively. The cluster mean of Instructors is 2.51, Inmates is 2.43 while that of Ex-convicts is 2.40, the grand mean of the respondents is 2.43 which means the Technical and Vocational Training programmes facilities in Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria are less adequate.

Research question 2

To what extent are the instructional methods of training (process) of technical and vocational training programmes effective in the correctional centres in North-West, Nigeria. *1.5 was used as a decision mean*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Respondents on to what Extent are the Instructional Methods of Training (Process) of Technical and Vocational Education Training Programmes are Effective in the Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria

S/N	Item Statement	X ₁	SD ₁	X ₂	SD ₂	X ₃	SD ₃	X _g	Rmrk
1.	Demonstration is used effectively in teaching vocational skills.	2.66	.883	2.4	.659	2.37	.678	2.46	Less Effective
2.	Games are used to make learning more engaging.	2.67	.793	2.58	.730	2.49	.804	2.56	Effective
3.	Questioning is used to encourage critical thinking.	2.67	.756	2.46	.772	2.36	.737	2.46	Effective
4.	Lecture is used to provide clear instructions.	2.54	.793	2.48	.683	2.48	.701	2.50	Effective
5.	Simulation is used to practice real-life scenarios.	2.94	.832	2.50	.763	2.51	.721	2.59	Effective
6.	Project-based learning is used to develop problem-	2.37	.51	2.5	.780	2.62	.731	2.5	Effective

	solving skills.		6	6			5	e	
7.	Discussion is encouraged to promote collaboration.	2.34	.478	2.54	.661	2.62	.691	2.53	Effective
8.	Field trips are organized to provide hands-on experience.	2.91	.697	2.51	.809	2.50	.759	2.59	Effective
Workshop Management									
9.	Equipment is properly arranged to ensure safety.	2.60	.769	2.61	.828	2.59	.790	2.58	Effective
10.	Tools are well-organized to promote efficiency.	2.54	.811	2.48	.724	2.55	.668	2.52	Effective
11.	Activities are adequately supervised to ensure safety.	2.54	.774	2.52	.683	2.50	.691	2.52	Effective
12.	Safety rules and regulations are clearly communicated.	2.43	.827	2.45	.733	2.47	.720	2.45	Less Effective
Classroom Management									
13.	Critical thinking is encouraged in vocational training.	2.59	.712	2.46	.762	2.57	.707	2.53	Effective
14.	Effective communication skills are taught in vocational training.	2.74	.896	2.46	.743	2.54	.658	2.55	Effective
15.	Creativity is encouraged in vocational training.	2.79	.740	2.47	.714	2.55	.738	2.57	Effective
16.	Collaboration is promoted in vocational training.	2.79	.611	2.55	.682	2.57	.708	2.61	Effective
Teaching Strategies									
17.	Activities are well-planned to promote learning.	2.73	.779	2.59	.739	2.63	.811	2.64	Effective
18.	Abstraction is used to help inmates understand complex concepts.	2.81	.728	2.54	.704	2.62	.700	2.63	Effective
19.	Application is used to help inmates apply theoretical knowledge.	2.70	.768	2.39	.755	2.60	.742	2.54	Effective
20.	Analysis is used to help inmates break down complex information.	2.61	.666	2.49	.663	2.61	.732	2.56	Effective

Evaluation									
21.	Summative assessment is used to evaluate inmates' learning at the end of the program.	2.66	.778	2.57	.680	2.60	.704	2.60	Effective
22.	Formative assessment is used to monitor inmates' progress during the program.	2.30	.521	2.24	.764	2.43	.718	2.33	Less Effective
23.	Process evaluation is used to assess the effectiveness of the vocational training program.	2.56	.810	2.32	.742	2.35	.753	2.38	Less Effective
24.	Outcome evaluation is used to assess the impact of the vocational training program.	2.47	.675	2.28	.720	2.31	.734	2.33	Less Effective
Cluster Mean		2.62	.734	2.48	.729	2.52	.725	2.52	Effective

Source: Field Work, 2025

Table 2 shows the Mean and Standard Deviation of the respondents on to what extent are the instructional methods of training of Technical and Vocational Training programmes in Correctional Centre in North-West, Nigeria. The table showed the mean of Instructors ranging from 2.30 to 2.94, the standard deviation also ranges from .474 to .883, the mean of Inmates also ranges from 2.24 to 2.61, the standard deviation ranges from .659 to .828 and the mean of Ex-convicts ranges from 2.31 to 2.63, the standard deviation also ranges from .658 to .811 respectively. The cluster mean of Instructors is 2.62, Inmates is 2.48 while that of Ex-convicts is 2.52, the grand mean of the respondents is 2.52 which means the instructional methods of training (process) of technical and vocational training programmes in the correctional centres in North-West, Nigeria are effective.

Research Hypothesis

Test of Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference among the mean responses of the instructors, inmates and ex-convicts on the efficiency training modules in Technical and vocational Education Training programmes in correctional centres in North-West, Nigeria. ANOVA analysis was used to test this hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 3: Result for Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on there is no Significant Difference Among the Mean Response of the Instructors, Inmates and ex-convicts on the training modules' Efficiency in Technical and Vocational Education Training programmes in correctional centres in North-West, Nigeria

Source of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value	Remark
Between Groups	9.929	2	4.965			

				57.164	.000	Rejected
Within Groups	30.326	350	.087			
Total	40.326	352				

ANOVA analysis result in Table 3 revealed that there is significant difference among the mean response of the instructors, inmates and ex-convicts on the content efficiency in Technical and vocational Training programmes in correctional centres in North-West, Nigeria with the F-value of 57.164 and the p- value of .000. Since the p- value is less than the confidence level of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$). The null hypothesis is therefore rejected at 0.05 (95%) confidence level. This implies that there is significant difference among the mean response of the instructors, inmates and ex-convicts on the content efficiency in Technical and vocational Training programmes in correctional centres in North-West, Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference among the mean response of instructors, inmates and ex-convicts on the effectiveness of the instructional methods of training (process) in technical and vocational education training programmes in the correctional centres in North-West Nigeria. ANOVA analysis was used to test this hypothesis at **0.05** level of significance

Table 4: Result for Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on there is No Significant Difference among the Mean Response of the Instructors, Inmates and Ex-Convicts on the Adequacy of Instructors of Technical and Vocational Training Programmes in Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria.

Source of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value	Remark
Between Groups	14.736	2	7.368	59.358	.000	Rejected
Within Groups	43.446	350	.124			
Total	58.182	352				

ANOVA analysis result in Table 4 revealed that there is significant difference among the mean response of the instructors, inmates and ex-convicts on the effectiveness of the instructional methods of training (process) in technical and vocational education training programmes in the correctional centres in North-West Nigeria with the F-value of 4.610 and the p- value of .011. Since the p- value is also less than the confidence level of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$). The null hypothesis is therefore rejected at 0.05 (95%) confidence level. This implies that there is significant difference among the mean response of the instructors, inmates and ex-convicts on the effectiveness of the instructional methods of training (process) in technical and vocational training programmes in the correctional centres in North-West Nigeria.

Discussion of the Findings

The study is an investigation on the efficacy and adequacy of technical and vocational education and training (TVET) resources for rehabilitation of inmates in correctional centres

in north-west Nigeria, based on two key areas which include; adequacy of facilities and instructional methods used in the Technical and Vocational Education Correctional Centres Training Programmes in North-west, Nigeria. Therefore, two (2) research objectives, two (2) research questions and two hypotheses were formulated and guided the conduct of the study.

In general, the study revealed that that Technical and Vocational Training programmes training modules are efficient in Correctional Centre in North-West, Nigeria, the instructors of Technical and Vocational Training programmes in Correctional Centre in North-West, Nigeria are adequate, the Technical and Vocational Training programmes facilities in Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria are less adequate, the instructional methods of training (process) of technical and vocational training programmes in the correctional centres in North-West, Nigeria are effective and The TVET training programmes in rehabilitating inmates in correctional centers in North- west, Nigeria is effective..

Conclusions

From the available data, the study revealed that Technical and Vocational Training programmes training modules are efficient in Correctional Centre in North-West, Nigeria, the instructors of Technical and Vocational Training programmes in Correctional Centre in North-West, Nigeria are adequate, the Technical and Vocational Training programmes facilities in Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria are less adequate, the instructional methods of training (process) of technical and vocational training programmes in the correctional centres in North-West, Nigeria are effective and The TVET training programmes in rehabilitating inmates in correctional centers in North- west, Nigeria is effective.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. The Government and all relevant stake holders should provide adequate facilities for Technical and Vocational Training programmes in Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria.
- ii. The government should encourage all the instructors to always use instructional methods of training (process) of technical and vocational training programmes in the correctional centres in North-West, Nigeria.

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